

Autogenerated Keywords for MOOCs

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Abstract. The assignment of metadata, particularly keywords, is often considered one of the least engaging tasks in creating and publishing MOOCs. Given the growing use of AI to streamline tedious processes, this study explores the potential of generative AI for automating keyword assignments. Specifically, we evaluated the performance of a large language model in generating keywords compared to human annotations. Our analysis focused on two key aspects: (1) the similarity between AI-generated and human-assigned keywords and (2) user preference - whether potential learners find AI-generated keywords more suitable than those assigned by humans - or not. To support this evaluation, we compiled a dataset containing both AI-generated keywords derived from course titles and descriptions (when available) and human-assigned keywords for 316 courses. This dataset served as the foundation for our similarity analysis. In parallel, we conducted a user study in which participants, acting as potential learners, assessed the relevance of AI-generated and human-assigned keywords. Their preferences were incorporated into the dataset and analyzed. Our findings provide insights into the effectiveness of AI-assisted metadata generation and its potential to enhance discoverability and classification in online learning platforms.

Keywords: metadata, keywords, auto generation, generative AI.

1 Introduction

Keywords help learners to quickly identify suitable courses. However, efficient filtering is only possible if the keywords have a certain quality. It can be hard to find keywords that describe the content of a course well, especially in a way that potential learners understand those and find the desired material. Above all, it is additional work for course teachers and administrators. This is why this task is often disregarded or performed without the necessary thoroughness. Even if teachers and administrators set the keywords it is still questionable if they meet learners' expectations.

Since we are interested in automated metadata generation, we investigated whether generative AI produces reasonable keywords. Our research questions are therefore:

- **Q1:** How similar are AI-generated keywords to human-assigned ones?
- **Q2:** Do users find AI-generated or human-assigned keywords more suitable for the course?

2 Related work

The research on automated keyword generation is not new. Already in 2004, natural language processing approaches were used by Yilmazel et al. [1]. This was before the era of large language models (LLM). The study found that manually assigned keywords were considered slightly better at this time.

Lee et al. used an LLM to generate keywords for scientific papers [2]. The idea was to determine trends in academic fields. Here, the keywords of the authors are the gold standard since they are the respective experts. This is why they were interested in a high similarity of the generated keywords to the authors' keywords.

Maragheh et al. published on the advantages of LLMs compared to classical methods for extracting keywords [3]. Their research interest was more in eCommerce applications, but we found it interesting how they included already existing metadata in the keyword generation process. Our keyword generation will also be based on existing course metadata.

3 Dataset

We needed a dataset of human- and AI-assigned keywords for courses for our studies. We consulted with the members of the MOOChub (a consortium of MOOC providers in the German-speaking area, www.moochub.org) and asked for course keywords. We received the human-annotated keywords for 316 courses from 6 course providers.

The dataset contains between 25 to 104 courses per platform. The median of assigned keywords for all platforms was 5 (mean: 5.6, std.: 3.7). Between 1 and 30 keywords were given, depending on the course. An overview is given in Table 1. Metadata (e.g. course descriptions) for these courses were freely available via the respective endpoints as described at www.moochub.org/about. The metadata of the courses (received December 2023) are the basis for our investigations and can be downloaded together with the keyword lists and the scripts for analysis (s. supporting material ³). We need to emphasize, that descriptions were not available for all courses. In these cases, keyword generation was based on the available metadata and the users' evaluation solely on the course title.

4 Methodology

Keywords were generated for each course based on the title and description (if available) using LLaMA 3 8b [4]. For the prompt and a detailed description of

³ https://osf.io/pc4r7/?view_only=c647dc1e4a58484495fef4d29dc3135

Table 1. Key parameters of the dataset.

Platform	No. courses	with description	No. keywords (median)
KI-Campus (AI campus)	25	15 (60.0 %)	2
LERNEN.cloud	28	16 (57.1 %)	6
openVHB	104	0 (0.0 %)	5
iMoox	94	76 (80.9 %)	5
openHPI	33	28 (84.4 %)	4
openSAP	32	31 (96.9 %)	12

observations, please see the supporting material. The LLM was asked to create exactly 10 keywords per course. The data set now contained the manual and AI-generated keywords for 316 courses.

4.1 Similarity of manual and generated keywords

Keywords given in German language were identified using googletrans-API⁴ and translated manually into English prior to the analysis. For the similarity check we converted all keywords to lower case letters only. We investigated the exact matches. This means the percentage of how many of the literal, manual keywords were also assigned by AI.

This will ignore some singular-plural mismatches, although the meaning of the keywords is similar or even the same. This is why we conducted the similarity analysis applying Levenshtein distance in the next step. We used the python package fuzzywuzzy⁵. We accepted a match with a similarity score of 90 (tight) and 80 (loose).

A purely orthographic similarity might not be sufficient in our opinion. In a third analysis we therefore searched for semantic similarity using the Python package spacy [5]. The similarity measure here was the cosine between the embedding vectors of two keywords. Again, we looked for a tighter and looser score. In this case 0.9 and 0.8 were considered matches, respectively.

The distribution of matches was analysed. We performed basic statistics and compared the similarity by method and by platform.

4.2 Evaluating users' preferences

We prepared a survey to check if users prefer the manually annotated or the AI keywords. The survey participants were presented the course title and description (if available) together with the lists of manually assigned and AI-generated keywords. The list lengths were roughly equalized. Per list, 4 to 6 keywords were selected randomly from all assigned keywords (also how many keywords were selected was randomized). All keywords were included in the list if fewer than 6

⁴ <https://pypi.org/project/googletrans/>

⁵ <https://pypi.org/project/fuzzywuzzy/>

keywords were assigned manually. The participants were asked to choose which list they found more fitting for the course or if they were equally good/bad.

The list with the AI-generated keywords was shown randomly on the right or left (the manual keyword list was on the other side). Together with the aligned list length, we disguised the manual and AI keywords. This way, the participants should not be able to identify the AI generated keywords by a pattern.

5 Results

5.1 Similarity of keywords

For exact matches, we found an average of 25 % (std.: 25 %) matches with between 0 and 100 % per course. In other words, there was a huge distribution, and we had to look closer at the details.

We investigated whether the platforms performed more or less equally. It turned out that for iMoox the AI found the highest rate of exact matches (mean: 33 %, std. 25 %). For 1 course with 5 keywords all of them were also assigned by the AI. The lowest rate of exact matches by the mean value were observed for LERNEN.cloud (mean: 12 %, std: 9 %) The highest amount of exact matches was only 25 %. The lowest median was found for KI-campus with 0 %. For more than half of the courses (18, 72 %), there was no exact match. For an overview of the distribution of exact matches, see Figure 1

Fig. 1. The distribution of exact matches per platform.

In total, we have 99 courses with no and 7 courses with 100 % exact matches across all platforms. We observed that the 100 % matches occurred when there are only very few manual keywords assigned (mean number of keywords: 2.4,

std.: 1.5). Since the AI always provided 10 keywords, the probability to hit these few keywords is increased. When there were no matches the keywords were often similar. For example, an additional word was missing (“certification” vs. “certification exam”).

Such similarities can be found with fuzzy searches. Here, the words or word groups need to be orthographically similar to a certain degree, but not the same. We applied the Levenshtein distance for this task. A score can be set to determine how similar the inputs need to be (100 is exact matches again, and 0 means no similarity). We used the scores 90 (tight) and 80 (loose) as thresholds based on experience values.

As expected, there was an increase compared to the exact matches. The mean of found matches increased to 26 % (std.: 25 %) for tight scoring and to 30 % (std.: 25 %) for loose scoring. For every platform there were still courses where no matches were observed.

Besides the orthographic similarity of keywords, we also checked for semantically similar keywords. We used the cosine similarity of embedded vectors provided by the Python package `spacy`. Here, we also investigated a tight (threshold: 0.9) and loose (threshold: 0.8) mode.

With the tight mode, we found that on average 33 % (std.: 27 %) of the generated keywords were similar to the manually assigned ones. For the loose mode, we found 55 % (std.: 27 %). As for the other methods, we again found very high standard deviations, pointing at a large distribution. Also, even in the loose mode, there were still 19 course with no matches. On the other hand, at least one match was found for the courses of the platforms LERNEN.cloud and openSAP.

The average number of matches increased from exact matches to fuzzy matches to semantic matches. This was, however, to expect because we allowed for a more diffuse definition of what is a match with every new method. For an overview of the distribution of percentages for matches see Figure 2.

We asked the LLM to use the metadata of the course. Since we already knew that not all courses contained a description attribute in their metadata, we wondered if this influenced the similarity. We found that for every method, the similarity was slightly better when there was a description available (Table 2).

Table 2. Average matches across all platforms dependent on the availability of course descriptions.

method	average matches [%] (std.)	
	without description	with description
exact	23 (25)	26 (25)
fuzzy (90)	25 (25)	28 (24)
fuzzy (80)	28 (26)	31 (25)
cosine (0.9)	31 (28)	35 (26)
cosine (0.8)	53 (28)	56 (27)

Fig. 2. The distribution of matches (in percent) by method.

5.2 Evaluating users' preferences

The similarity between AI-generated and manually assigned keywords provided insights into how well the AI aligned with the choices made by course teachers and administrators. Considering what keywords are for (searching and filtering by learners), we should also ask how well learners' expectations on keywords for a specific course were met. We therefore conducted a survey with randomly selected people from different age groups, gender, and professions. We got a good mixture of people representing a broad spectrum of potential learners.

We managed to gather the participant views on the keywords for all 316 courses. In total, the participants voted 156 times (49 %) for the AI-generated keywords, 117 times (37 %) for the manually assigned ones, and 43 times (14 %) for undecided. If we asked whether the AI was at least as good as the human annotators we got 199 courses (63 %) fulfilling this condition.

We grouped the survey results by platform to see if there was an effect. The results are shown in Figure 3. For KI-Campus, we observed the lowest preference for the manually assigned keywords (12 %). The highest preference for manually assigned keywords was found for openVHB with 45 %. It was also the only platform for which the voting for the manual keywords was higher than for the manually assigned ones. Taking into account the undecided as the AI performed not worse than the human annotator we can say that the AI outperformed the human in the task of finding fitting keywords.

We compared KI-Campus and openVHB keywords and course metadata to get insights into why the performance was so different. For KI-Campus, 15 courses (60 %) had a description, while for openVHB, no course had one. The availability of course descriptions seemed not to have an effect. The manual keywords for the KI-campus course were often very generic (e.g. "education"). Also, only very few keywords were given (lowest number of keywords for all platforms:

Fig. 3. The participants' choices for preferred keywords for a course grouped by platforms.

median = 2, maximum = 4). openVHB had 5 keywords for most courses (median: 5, maximum: 5). The keywords were also way more specific about the course. While it seems that the availability of descriptions not had an effect, the efforts that the course teachers and administrators put into the keywords is recognized by the learners.

6 Conclusion

We have investigated to what extent AI generates keywords that are in accordance with course teachers and administrators. We looked for literally the same keywords, for a more fuzzy definition of orthographic similarity using Levenshtein distance for scoring and semantic similarities with cosine similarity of embedded vectors. We found that the similarity strongly depends on how much effort was spent on manually assigning keywords. Some platforms use only a few rather simple and generic keywords, while the AI tries to find relatively specific keywords for a given course. It was rather unlikely that AI found literally the same keywords as humans do, although it happened for some courses. Even if we widened the definition of a match to a certain degree of orthographic similarity the number of matches did not increase much. When we applied semantic similarity measures we saw a larger increase in matches, especially for the loose definition of similarity.

What we can say is that AI often found keywords for courses with a meaning that was close to what a human annotator had in mind. These might be synonyms or a rephrasing. This helps course teachers and administrators to quickly identify keywords. The suggestions might also inspire them to look at the course from a different angle.

Above all, our survey showed that the AI-generated keywords were often considered more fitting to the courses by the participants. Depending on the platform, the participants preferences point more or less strongly at the AI assigned keywords. This effect was stronger when the human annotators only use very few, generic keywords. AI always tried to find very specific keywords, even if only a title was present. The participants preferred such specific keywords since they help to decide if a course is suited for the learner.

Our conclusion from this study is that automated keyword generation using generative AI/LLMs is a helpful tool. It not only eases teachers' and administrators' task of providing metadata but might also give them new points of view about their course. This is helpful, because often learners have a different perspective, as shown by our survey. The AI is therefore capable to suggest useful keywords for most courses. It is still necessary to review the suggested keywords by a teacher or administrator.

We expect that in the future, the suggestions by AI will improve further. Especially if new, specifically trained models for this task will be applied. However, even an LLM out-of-the-box without further training performed very well. Generative AI will play a growing role not only in the production of learning materials but also in the creation and maintenance of metadata.

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